

Implementation and Challenges of Pharmacogenetics in Clinical Practice: A Comparative Study between Lebanon, Qatar and KSA

Who we are ?

We are a team of researchers from Qatar University (Doha, Qatar) and Beirut Arab University (Beirut, Lebanon). We invite you to participate in this **IRB Approved Research Study**.

You will be asked to complete an anonymous **4-minute questionnaire**. Please read the consent form and consider whether you want to be involved in the study. Your valuable insights will contribute to understanding the current state and identifying potential areas of improvement.

Please contact Dr. **Dalal Hammoudi** (dhammoude@qu.edu.qa) if you have any questions about this study.

* Indicates required question

1. Informed Consent Form- Questionnaire *

Purpose:

The Informed Consent Form is designed to confirm that the participant has been given all relevant information about the research and their role within it, and how both the researcher and participant are protected.

Please read the following statements fully and carefully. By proceeding to take the questionnaire, you are giving your consent.

Summary

I volunteer to take part in this research questionnaire. I understand that the research aims to collect data on the implementation and Challenges of Pharmacogenetics in Clinical Practice.

1. I confirm that I have been given a copy, and read, the Participant Information Sheet and fully understood the information it contained.

2. I understand that my participation in this project is voluntary. I will not be paid for my involvement. I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without reason.

3. I have read and understood that all data provided will be treated in strict confidence, and that my name and organisation will be anonymised. I understand that my data will be kept, securely, for a period of 5 years after the interview, in accordance with the Data Protection Act 1998.

By proceeding to take this questionnaire, I agree to take part in this research project and to the above statements.

Check all that apply.

I Agree to participate

2. Section A: Demographic Information *

1. Age (years)

Mark only one oval.

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-55

Above 55

3. **2. Gender ***

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

4. **Country of residence**

Mark only one oval.

Qatar

Lebanon

5. **3. Occupation ***

Mark only one oval.

Nurse

Pharmacist

Clinician

Researcher in Biology/Biochemistry

Academic

Other

6. **If you chose the option 'other', please specify:**

7. **4. Name of the Institution/Company ***

8. **6. Current Position**

9. **7. Years of Experience in Clinical Practice or research (if scientist/ Academia): ***

Mark only one oval.

- < 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-20 years
- > 20 years

10. **Section B: Implementation of Pharmacogenetics ***

8. Are you familiar with the concept of pharmacogenetics ?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

11. **9. Have you attended or given educational talks on pharmacogenetics in the past 2 years? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Many
- Few
- One
- None

12. **10. Have you integrated pharmacogenetic testing into your clinical practice? or your research (if scientist/ Academia) ?**

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, routinely
- Yes, occasionally
- No, but considering
- No, not interested

13. **11. If you have integrated pharmacogenetics, please describe the process (Open-ended response) :**

14. **Section B: Obstacles in Implementation**

*

12. Identify the top 5 obstacle(s) for bringing Pharmacogenetics into clinical practice

Check all that apply.

- Test cost and reimbursement
- Insufficient physician knowledge or awareness
- Physician scepticism or lack of interest
- Unclear test interpretation
- Limited evidence for clinical utility: clinical benefit and cost-effectiveness
- Unclear or lack of guidelines
- Unavailability of test, technology, infrastructure, manpower or experts
- Lack of adequate counsellors or adequate communication of results
- Electronic medical records integration and clinical decision support
- Data from different populations or ethnicities
- Insufficient public understanding or awareness
- Lack of funding, investment or support
- Lack of legislative mandate or endorsement
- Integration into clinical workflow
- Turn-around time and efficiency
- Suboptimal ethical regulations for information protection
- Data management and bioinformatics
- Inefficient administrative and regulative bodies
- Lack of standardization of genotyping tests and results across laboratories
- Disconnect between clinical practitioners and researchers
- Patient expectations or concerns
- Need for large-scale genetic screening
- Unrealistic ideas to apply large-scale genetic testing
- Lack of alternative treatments

15. **13. Please provide details or elaborate on the obstacles you selected in the previous question: (Open-ended response)**

16. **Section D: Future Considerations**

15. In your opinion, what measures could be taken to overcome the obstacles faced in implementing pharmacogenetics in clinical practice? (Open-ended response)

17. **16. Do you believe that pharmacogenetics has the potential to significantly improve patient outcomes in clinical practice?** *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Undecided

18. **17. How interested would you be in learning about pharmacogenomics?** *

Mark only one oval.

- Not interested
- Slightly
- Interested
- Very Intrested

19. **18. What specific pharmacogenomics topics, if any, would you like to learn about? ***

Mark only one oval.

- Cardiovascular diseases
- Cancer chemotherapy
- Neurodegenerative disorders
- Immune Suppressants
- Infectious diseases
- Psychiatric disorders
- Complex diseases such as Diabetes Mellitus
- Pain management

20. **Thank you for completing this survey. Your participation is greatly appreciated. Your responses will help in understanding the challenges and opportunities associated with the implementation of pharmacogenetics in clinical practice. If you have any additional comments or suggestions, please feel free to provide them below:**

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